

Cost Analysis on L-shape Composite Component Manufacturing

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Abstract

In this work, cost analysis in connection with quality of L-shape composite parts made by Autoclave and Out-of-Autoclave (OOA) techniques was carried out. Both convex and concave molds were used. The cost components include material cost, labor cost, tool and equipment costs (purchasing, maintenance and depreciation cost) and energy cost. A few steps can be taken in parallel for both autoclave and OOA processes. The results indicate that the production time and cost would be saved by using parallel steps. The results show that using OOA leads to lower production cost. The higher material cost associated with OOA process is compensated mainly by the savings on equipment cost.

1. Introduction

Composites are the fastest growing "materials" because of their light weight, good damage tolerance and corrosion resistance [1]. Composites are widely applied in aerospace, wind turbines, sporting goods, automobile, shipbuilding and civil infrastructure areas. Modern composites manufacturing techniques include autoclave molding, filament winding, pultrusion, liquid composite molding, and thermoplastic composites [2].

Conventional composite manufacturing such as autoclave processing is expensive due to extensive labor and equipment costs [1, 3]. Over the past several years, there have been efforts to find less expensive methods for the manufacturing of composites. Out-of Autoclave (OOA) is a manufacturing technique that has received a lot of attention. The difference between autoclave manufacturing and OOA is that in the former one,

pressure is used while only vacuum is used in the latter technique. The result is that less expensive equipment (ovens) is used as compared to more expensive autoclaves. However, due to the lack of pressure, it is important that the resin has sufficiently low viscosity to flow and wet the fibers. New types of prepregs need to be available. These can be more expensive than conventional autoclave prepregs and the quality of the part needs to be compared [4]. Detailed cost breakdowns for the two manufacturing processes are presented in this paper. The analysis shows that some portion of the process can be done in parallel, which can reduce the total cost. In addition, quality of the part in terms of microscopic appearance, and mechanical properties are examined, in conjunction with the cost.

2. L-Shape Composites Parts

In order to make the comparison study, L shape composite parts were produced. The L shaped parts provide some degree of complexity, as compared to just flat samples, so that different aspects of manufacturing may enter into the picture. A photo of the sample is shown in Figure 1. These parts can be made using molds of L shape. Both the convex side and concave side of the mold were used. The samples have very good quality. The void content of the samples is lower than 1%. Figure 2 is the Microscope picture for the corner surface of the sample.

Figure 1. Photo of the autoclave sample

Figure 2. Corner surface of the sample

2.1. Autoclave concave and convex L-shape composite parts

For the autoclave processing, prepregs obtained from Newport composites (NCT 301) were used. The main processing are: Cutting the materials (NCT 301), Preparing tools, Layup prepregs, Bagging, Placing assembly into autoclave, Curing, Removal of the sample from mold, Inspection, and Finishing steps. The layup consists of a total of 8 plies by the stacking sequence [0-90-0-90-90-0-90-0] on the L-shape mould. The size of each ply for convex sample is 12"×4". And the size of each ply for concave sample is 10.5"×4". Debulking was done after layup of the first ply, and then subsequently after every 2 plies. The curing cycle is shown in Figure 3. The pressure was 60 psi.

Figure 3. Autoclave curing cycle

2.2. OOA concave and convex composite parts

The equipment used for OOA process is an oven, which is less expensive than autoclave. The material used in this manufacturing process is Cycom 5320[5]. To make the sample to have the same thickness with autoclave samples, 4 Cycom 5320 plies by the direction [0/90/90/0] were used (CYCOM 5320 comes in the form of fabrics, while NCT 301 comes in the form of unidirectional layers). The size of each ply for convex sample is 12"×4", and the size of each ply for concave sample is 10.5"×4". Debulking took place after each ply. The pressure for Cycom 5320 is 28.5 Hg vacuum[6]. Figure 4 shows a photo of the sample and the curing cycle [5] is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4. OOA concave samples

Figure 5. OOA curing cycle

3. Cost Analysis

The cost components considered in this analysis include: raw material cost, labor cost, tool and equipment costs (purchasing, maintenance and depreciation costs) and energy cost [7, 8].

3.1 Materials cost:

Raw materials cost is the purchase price of the amount of the prepreg, release agent, bleeder, breather, release film, vacuum bag, and sealant tape. The cost is the sum of each type of materials. Each type of raw material cost is the amount multiplying the unit price. When the prepreps are cut, the waste of the materials is not avoidable. So the waste of the prepreg should be included. Table 1 shows the material price for making the 4 sample products.

Table 1. Materials price for OOA concave samples

Raw Material	Supplier	Price	Unit Price
Prepreg	Cytec	\$25/lb	\$0.05/g
Release Agent	Airtech	\$147.72/L	\$0.148/ml
Breather	Airtech	\$7.02/ft	\$1.404/sq-ft
Release Film	Airtech	\$5.61/ft	\$1.122/sq-ft
Vacuum Bag film	Airtech	\$2.73/ft	\$0.546/sq-ft
Polyethylene Film	Polytarp product	\$0.5/ft	\$0.083/sq-ft
Sealant Tape	General sealant	\$191.2/case	\$4.78/single

3.2 Cutting and layup cost

Cutting and layup were performed by hand. Detailed layup steps are shown in Table 2. The cutting and layup time depend on the size and number of the plies, the thickness of the material and the shape of the model. The labor cost of \$37.63 can be obtained by multiplying the labor rate, assuming \$15/hour, by the total labor time shown at the end of Table 2.

3.3 Equipment and tool cost:

Equipments and tools costs include the energy cost, depreciation cost and maintaining cost. Energy cost is the cost of the electric energy which is used during the manufacturing process. The straight line method is used for calculate the depreciation cost for the machines which are used for making the samples. For this study, the depreciation cost for each sample is the daily depreciation cost of the equipments. The third item is maintenance cost. Daily maintaining cost is used for each sample, since it takes about one day to make one sample. The total equipments and tools cost is the sum of these three terms:

Equipment and Tools Cost = Depreciation Cost + Energy Cost + Maintenance Cost

where:

$$\text{Depreciation Cost} = \frac{\text{purchasing price} - \text{salvage value}}{\text{lifecycle} \times 300 \text{ (days)}}$$

$$\text{Energy Cost} = \text{Electricity Rate} \times \text{Processing Time}$$

$$\text{Maintenance Cost} = \frac{\text{Annual Maintenance Cost}}{300 \text{ (days)}}$$

Table 2. Layup steps and time

Process	Time (min)
Cleaning the mold	5
Cutting Prepreps	3
Cutting Breather	1
Cutting Release film	1
Cutting Vacuum bag	1
Cutting Plastic	0.5
Applying release agent	32
Layup 1st and 2nd prepreg	8
Applying preparing consolidation bag	10
Applying consolidation place bag	5
Consolidation for 10min	10
Remove bag	5
3rd prepreg down	4
Replace bag	5
Consolidation for 10min	10
Remove bag	5
4rd prepreg down	4
Applying preparing consolidation bag	10
Applying consolidation place bag	5
Testing bag sealing	5
Placing the tool in the Autoclave	8
Removing tool from the Autoclave	8
Removing Composite from the Mold	5
Total time	150.50

3.4 Total cost

The total cost for each sample is the sum of materials cost, cutting and layup (labor) cost and equipment and tool cost [9]. The total cost and cost breakdown for composite manufacturing process are shown in Table 3 and Figure 6.

Table 3. Total cost for the four types of samples

Cost (\$)	OOA Convex	OOA Concave	Autoclave Convex	Autoclave Concave
Material	18.37	18.2	10.94	9.88
Labor	37.63	38.88	50.5	53.15
Equipment	15.09	15.09	41.45	41.45
Total	71.09	72.17	102.89	104.48

Figure 6. Cost breakdown and comparison

4. Process Improvement

From the cost breakdown (shown in Table 3 and Figure 6), one can find that for each type of manufacturing method, labor cost occupies a large part of the total cost. So layup process is labor sensitive. Take the OOA-convex manufacturing process [5] as an example, the step of applying release agent needs 32 minutes, 2 minutes for applying and 30 minutes for waiting as shown in Table 2. This waiting time can be used to do other steps at the same time. During the waiting time the mold is occupied, so one can only operate the steps

which do not need mold as parallel process shown in Table 4. For example, one can do cutting materials and preparing the vacuum bags during waiting time in applying release agent step. Thus, the total manufacturing time and cost could be reduced by using parallel process (Figure 7). Table 4 and Figure 7 show the improvement of manufacturing process. The total cost of the process in parallel for each kind of manufacturing process is calculated and shown in Table 5. The comparison of the cost for the process in full steps and process in parallel is shown in Table 5 and Figure 7.

Table 4. Improved process with parallel layup steps

Process		Time (min)
Cleaning the mold		5
Apply release agent	Cutting prepregs	32
	Cutting breather	
	Cutting release film	
	Cutting vacuum bag	
	Cutting plastic	
	Preparing consolidation bag1	
Preparing consolidation bag2		
Layup 1st and 2nd prepreg		8
Place the bag 1		5
Consolidation for 10min		10
Remove bag		5
3rd prepreg down		4
Replace bag		5
Consolidation for 10min		10
Remove bag		5
4rd prepreg down		4
Place the bag 2		5
Testing bag sealing		5
Placing the tool in the autoclave		8
Removing tool from the Autoclave		8
Removing composite from the mold		5
Total time		124

Table 5. Cost comparison with improved processes

Cost (\$)	OOA Convex	OOA Concave	Autoclave Convex	Autoclave Concave
Material	18.37	18.2	10.94	7.61
Labor	31	32	39.5	42.4
Equipment	15.09	15.09	41.45	41.45
Total	64.46	65.29	91.89	91.46

Figure 7. Cost comparison for series and parallel processes

5. Conclusion

In this paper, the autoclave and OOA manufacturing process for both concave and convex L-shape composite components were described. The materials, size of the sample, the layup process and the cure cycle conditions for these two different composite manufacturing methods were illustrated. The cost breakdown for the composite production process was analyzed and identified. The costs for concave and convex samples which are made by autoclave and OOA methods respectively are compared in the end. In addition, an improvement for the composite production process was proposed. And it shows that the cost can be reduced by using parallel production process. The cost analysis indicates that using

parallel steps would save production time and hence processing time related cost. The results of the experiments and analysis conclude that using OOA will lead to least total production cost. The higher material cost associated with OOA process will be compensated mainly by the savings on equipment cost.

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